

The Curvature Gambit – Mass Variation over Time ?

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July 25, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the Quark masses series and the framework of varying curvature, analysis of mass variation overtime will be presented. The analysis be comparing the inverse symmetry of coupling constants lack of variance over short temporal periods in order to predict a lack of variance of mass terms overtime.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We presented recently the EMT symmetry by the terms (1.45) and (1.46):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\mu^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.45)$$

In addition, the Tau:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (\tau^-)] + \gamma \quad (1.46)$$

If reader is familiar with the 8T two symmetry breaking – inward to generate mass:

$$8 - (1)$$

Moreover, outward to generate a ripple on the matric tensor given by the term:

$$8 + (1)$$

We have found the decreasing pattern among the three generations of Quark by using the Quark mass series of the 8T, which combined the estimated mass of both Quarks of each generation to a single number. As a result, we concluded that the heaviest generation is the first (T-B), and the first (U-D) is the third. We predicted a total mass of the fourth generation, to be 55-56 times lighter than first, 0.113 Mev. Mass in the 8T is curvature converging to a point.

$$19,600 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 56 \rightarrow 0.113 \dots$$

The above pattern was found by rescaling the values of the and the, as presented below, that is by two versions of the mass equations (2) or (2.1).

$$19,600 * 9 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow \frac{56}{9} =$$

$$176,400 \rightarrow 1400 \rightarrow 6.3$$

The two versions are presented as it is unknown whether the factor of nine is repeating itself for the fifth family and beyond.

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9} \quad (2)$$

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} \quad (2.1)$$

$$N_E = 2E ; E \geq 1$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T thesis fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. The question we will analyze now is concerning the actual mass of each generation. Is it time invariant or time variant? Since the manifold is being in constant expansion, due to pressure from distinct manifolds, it gets more and more flat. As time goes by, the coupling terms getting weaker and weaker overtime, despite the actual value of the N_V is increasing. That is by the principle of least curvature, which take the value of net to average total variation pair for each coupling term;

$$\frac{N_V}{T_V} \rightarrow R \quad (2.2)$$

$$0.111 > 0.1 > 0.039 > 0.008 \dots \rightarrow 0$$

The coupling constants series and the mass series are inverse symmetries. One describe curvature diverging, the other curvature converging. According to this analysis, if the coupling terms are holding as time invariant, so does the masses of the fermions. It can not vary, what is varying is the generation. As the arrow of time is dictating weaker interactions over the primordial development, it is also indicating smaller and lighter generation masses overtime. As far as one can see, there is no flexibility in the actual values of the masses; there is no indication in the 8T that they are subject of short temporal variance. The argument is mainly supported by the inverse symmetry of the coupling constants series being time invariant at short period scales. That does not mean that the mass can not vary via a manipulation or an absorbent of particles into it, all it means is that without it its value are invariant. It comes to an agreement with the conservation of curvature, which state that no curvature can escape the manifold, it was presented as part of the coupling constants and refer only to N_V but it would apply to the inverse symmetry of mass.

$$\oint_{t=0}^{t=Z} (ds)(s_0 \times R) \left(\sum_{V=0}^{\infty} N_V \right) \in s \quad (3)$$

One final point, if the masses of the particles were a subject to variance over any periods of time, it would have been much harder to classify the particles. The fact that physicists were able to measure time and location independently the masses of particles, indicate that the variance is generation oriented exclusively and not time oriented toward a certain particle. That is in agreement with the Quark mass series and the Primordial series.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)